

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

ΕΣΧΑΤΟΝ ΠΥΡ: OVERMAN AS HISTORY

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Abstract

History is bound to an opposite destination in the form of sheer incarnation. This embodies becoming, the underlying force from within the cosmos, the purest action. All these traits are harmonic into one Single Mover as necessary historical gore. This is the ΕΣΧΑΤΟΝ ΠΥΡ, the *Ultimate Fire*, from the Greek ἔσχατος and πῦρ, meaning “last” and “fire” this latter in the Heraclitean sense of all-steering Rational Agent. This impetus the Overman incarnates and presides over into the Triad of Power formed by himself, Being as Power and Becoming as Increase in Power, all focusing on his own Person. The whole process culminates into will as Will-to-the Overman as a well-defined antithetical Body, at once directed unto the future and the past. For this supreme state of affairs the whole force of the universe and the core of perpetual change are required, as one. Literary parts and semiotic images are included.

Keywords: ontology, history, will, cosmology, superhuman, metaphysics, semiotics, physics, visual arts, literature

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The Eskaton Pyr: an Introduction

In sheer metaphysical terms, Becoming (κίνησις) proves opposed to Permanent Being (ἐπίμονον ὄν) not to Being as such (τὸ ὄν, τὸ εἶναι), in whose respects no positive opposition can be in principle assumed, by its thus constituting one of its leading traits, this latter aspect as stressed in the notion of *Triad of Power* and as now dwelt upon as embodied in one single historical mover and perennial force. That is, touching the following premise [1]:

Triad (of Power, Overhuman): This triad is formed by Being as Power as Power (*Esse Ipsum Potentiae*) under the garb of reinvigorating Source, Becoming as Increase of Power and the Condition of Power, all focusing on the singular action (*Fortitudo in Acto*) of the Overman, as the specular counterpart of Being as Power. The Overman is one with the unrestrainable Becoming through the medium of his own will as a premise for change, Being maintaining its external status of Source. It differs from the Ontological Triad on account of its admitting no dialectical counterpart in terms of powerlessness (as Man or Shadow),

and of its entailing an ultimate Ontological Fusion as Radiation still in the person of the Overman to take place into the phase of the potentiating return as final definition of the *Ens* (Return of Power).

This triad embodies the deepest energetic synthesis to be possibly conceived, as incarnated in the frame of the Overman precisely, with Becoming as a fundamental trait within the continuously changing Physical *Ens*, and as by definition endowed with a very aim. That is, he is at once the incarnation of Becoming as the Ultimate Act of the latter, a situation, as is known, traditionally assigned to Being, which is now looked upon, within this very union, as an element dwelling in the aforementioned terms of *Esse Ipsum Potentiae*, thus involving an Absolute Value and Supreme Act, still most dynamic in itself as related to the Overman, the latter possessing these same specular qualities. A proportional relationship is therefore established. To add more, still by way of introduction, and in terms this time of Hegelian, hence Heraclitean dialectics, this latter as the most fiery embodiment of the primordial, hence most veritable *Logos* [2] reasoning in an antithetical turn of mind had beyond doubt a substantial impact on twentieth century history. For its geopolitical effects are still visible to-day, and shall still be visible, by their obeying to the natural rule of the intrinsic contrast. Thus, again, the rational force of the *Logos*, wherefrom the Baconian idea of dominion over the entity (*Ens*, τὸ ἐόν) originated, plays still a fundamental role [3] under the dialectical garb now specifically taken into account. The standpoint is accordingly *objective*, with the main argument herewith presented according to terms comparable, vaguely, to what in the *Phenomenology of Spirit* (*Phänomenologie des Geistes*) is found as *Geist* [4], with no other subdivision needed, and as further exceeded into one overhuman mover and frame. For, by aid of recorded facts, through solemn inscriptions graven within the rock as immortal human memories, arising alone yet in unison, with a sentiment of *tangible vengeance in waiting*, as a dazzling veritable *Shadow*,

at Tadmor, at Nineveh, at Hattusa, at Mycenae, at legendary Thule itself, one may be enabled to positively say that there do must exist a unified force standing beyond all this, hence beyond human collective sacrifice, action and effort in necessary gore as themselves in the end forming the body of history. The main standpoint is thus as follows: the Overman renders the latter, by events thus proving at once grandiose and tragic, referred to *the natural need for a core, as a manifestation of himself, of Being as Power and of Becoming as an Increase of Power* [5], in reference hence to no greater dynamic synthesis to be possibly conceived, and as still focusing on his own intangible frame to be found as one with these events. He is therefore an *Unum Absolutum*, the central revealer of a flowing dynamism, in the essence most self-affirmative in necessary historical gore. There exists, accordingly, an *overman-centrism*, as it were, behind and beyond the Real, hitherto hidden or otherwise unperceived, save in the vague yet most veritable form of myth [6]. In its regards, history, excepting Antiquity and the Middle Ages, to be from now on fathomed as both the primordial hence truthful *origin*, has been thus far a mere *Shade*, the most intangible and obscure one to enter the mind, upon the Overman being *again perceived as the unparalleled antithetical goal and destination*. This cannot but touch the essence of man, hence of *the human in an extended sense*, the former not being able to prove altogether one with the latter, too imperfect, both physically and spiritually, proving his indeed obscure character [7]. Hence *Copernican Revolution* in the terms of directing force is involved, which force, as it shall be seen, is the very incarnation of one self-recurring, hence self-referential infinite increasing its inner impetus to ∞ . Upon these very grounds, the greatest achievements of mankind can be looked upon as all an unconscious manifestation of the Overman, by his own embodying the essence (antithetical) of the human as *Unum Absolutum* precisely, which is again the very beacon by which the individual of proven value comes naturally, yet still most selectively, through his own faculty and decision, driven [8]. No one can be possibly sheltered: *the Force is yonder*, infinitely behind and beyond, as thus one with the very gore shed into deep historical Becoming, whatsoever single action done within the present human, no matter how epochal in kind. In further terms exceeding those otherwise found as to the Aristotelian-Thomistic conception of *Analogia Potentiae*, thus on the latter as projected into the *Act*, more may be observed, as again referred to the immortal hence most true and still reddening dawn of the Hellenic Logos (for it is still, ontologically, in its own fiery infancy). That is, the notion of *Unum Absolutum*, as defining a centrality, may well be exceeded in that of *Ēskhaton Pyr* (ἔσχατον πῦρ) or *Ultimate Fire*, as still conveying this same centrality, yet under a garb otherwise imbued with a primal dazzling dynamism. This cannot but be bound to the very incarnation of Becoming, with reference still to the immortal Heraclitean dictum τὰ δὲ πάντα οἰακίζει κεραινός [9] as denoting the unparalleled force in the ever-living Thunderbolt, the highest attribute and epiclesis of Zeus (the same Germanic Thor, the Hittite Teshub, the Roman Jupiter, into one Indo-European

tradition [10]), all-directing, over all holding its sudden dominion, yet self-exceeded as spiral-like in kind (κοχλιώδης), to the infinite extending its centrifugal impetus, and with traits *unlimited and indeterminate* altogether akin to those found in the ἄπειρον of Anaximander [11]. Intensely hereinto, events weld altogether, thus wearing an aspect of sheer indeterminacy, as flowing in reference to a continual generation and corruption, and as thus requiring a Very Agent, both internal, as immanent beating heart, whose vital force lies stealthily manifested, and external, as a directing Beacon wherein *Energy exceeds Reason within Reason itself*. This process is at once affirmative and contrasting, for adversity antithetically fuels the impetus, that is, the more the former, the more the latter as self-overcoming, into thus a continual process self-increasing in potency unto a point that shall reach infinity, as it shall be seen. In an attempt at fathoming a point of agreement between the notions of ἀρχή (principle, origin) and τροπή (metamorphosis, change), as in fact radically opposed, the Overman embodies them both as thus endowed with these very fiery qualities, and again unto a very situation that shall, precisely as the Heraclitean Thunderbolt, direct and judge the dignified Ens, with its own inevitable amount of historical gore left behind into the trail of the Cosmic Fire (for history on the planet earth yields before, and in fact derives from the superior Energy within the universe). Into the grandest moments of this unrelenting thread (in whose regard a *backwards direction* not even the mightiest deity, as proving by definition impotent towards the by-gone, and its irreversible sentence, is able to assume), the Overman grows a conqueror *towards both the latter and the present as a unchangeable certainty, and the future as an open possibly*, by his thus again incarnating the most dynamic trait into the Triad of Power, which is a unified Force into his own person as most distant from Stillness or Chaos, hence from sheer ontological Falsity [12]. For no single individual alone, no matter how exceptional his character might possibly prove, can minimally suit the supreme gravity, responsibility, and tragic burden in the whole of historical events, still on account of the present status of the human proving so dreadfully limited, and now in further reference to the immortal notion of καλοκαγαθία, which notion has been illustrated in photonic-geometric terms [13]. The comparison is thus with the World Spirit (Weltgeist), or very moment in which the Soul of the Real reaches its own phase of full historical awareness as thus referred to a *mere mortal* driven forth into his own imperfection as proving both last defeat on a crucial battlefield and in the end, further, total dissolution, as Hegel did at Jena.

Equation of Power and Overhuman Advent

History reaches its fiery zenith touching the intangible action from a sheer overhuman Personification as Becoming, to which the sole *character of the purest adamantine sublimity* may be referred, when thus reverberating its own primordial Steel [14] into still fiery collective terms, such as those to be found at its very dawn (for the origin can never prove negative), in thus

the first theocratic states of southern Mesopotamia, and later, in the Assyrian and Mycenaean monarchies, in the Athens of Pericles, in Rome during Augustus (including the tragic solemnity in the Varian Disaster of 9 A.D., which disaster altered forever, through the will of the young Arminius, the whole course of European history, hence of history itself [15]), in the Empire of Charlemagne, in Scotland as ruled by Robert the Bruce, and so forth. It is not much to say that this clearly signifies a *Disclosedness* (in terms of crucial sheer ἀλήθεια, or a Heideggerian one, even), although with an impetus naturally addressed to the future, yet, for the same reason *feeding with equal strength and determination the by-gone*, which not even the mighty volition of a god can alter. Herein, again, a catalyzation is required, *into one overhuman Body as the very essence of corporeality, as thus opposed to its own intangible Shadow* [16], as a requisite of glaringness mirroring unto perfection the self-regenerating vigour from Being as Power as one with it, and of no evolution as generally received, since the process is spiral-like in kind. On the one hand, entailing thus a sheer overhuman conception of history, the most so ever, on the other, the ultimate opposition to Chaos, ontological feebleness, and uncertainty as a personification in a most tangible, light-related manner [17], the Overman thus catalyzes upon his own gleaming skin, gleaming when mirroring unto perfection the eternally self-regenerating vigour from Being as Power [18], the whole force of history, by his manifesting himself, through epochal events in a spiral-like, self-referential manner as the most fiery manifestation of Becoming, throughout a process thus continually self-overcoming since always most identical to itself. Herein, no evolution whatsoever can find any room, for this manifestation proves eternally recurring by an increasing power exceeding the category evolution at issue itself, as generally received. This implies the existence of antagonizing forces as by definition forming the substratum of Becoming, the substratum, therefore, not its own essence, which essence remains dazzlingly bound to a self-referential, in a spiral-like manner closing on itself Increase in Power. A want, fundamental in kind, is moreover necessary, in order to trigger off an overcoming respecting a previous status. This want may well be transformed into the affirmative terms of Adversity, for the latter fuels Energy, antithetically, that is, the more the former, the more the motivation in surpassing a by-gone situation, by thus reducing it to ashes though a continually self-increasing in potency progression, which progression the Overman, as a beacon, presides over. Having briefly premised this, the substance is as follows: the proportional relationship (proportio-relatio) of the Overman with man is to be found within *concrete action itself*, the latter alone granting results, in reference to epochal events more especially, with his unimaginably superior Frame always embodying, still in a most tangible manner, a necessary specular and *most selective* aim (for else the ontological unworthy shall recur as well, which is inadmissible, a metaphysical blasphemy indeed, as to the nobility in the *Purest Ens* [19]. Thus, in terms of necessarily selective goal:

The more the decadence, the more the energetic accumulation (latent) for the adequation to the Overman and to his Era

Or

The more the difference between the Overman and man (which difference, although already abysmal since antithetical [20]), yet, it increases in a time of historical decline), the more the impetus for his own return before the dazzling Presence of Being as Power as favoring individual excellence

This aforementioned process *should not be looked upon as ensuing forthwith*, it instead requiring a given length of time as, for instance, the one to be found between the last centuries of the Roman Empire (fourth and fifth century) and the splendor in the maturity of the Middle Ages (twelfth, thirteenth and fourteenth century), by thus regarding the ensuing Renaissance in a minor ontological gravity, in terms both of action, or even more so theological, or else. The historical Real, although noble in its essence yet dreadful in its own particulars, proves not enough remunerated as to a superior greatness, with the inevitable result of the rise of what turns out to be, in terms of temporal progression, or again Becoming, the opposite, that is, the Person of the Overman in selective waiting. Decline, as therefore one with general ontological stillness, lies therefore directly proportional to the increasing-in-power spiral-like recurrence of the Overman as embodying, in his own very frame, the very aim of Becoming: the dazzling opposite state of affairs within whose antithetical (and cosmological, as it shall be seen) character the meaning of history is now under consideration, which meaning has been in many ways fathomed throughout the centuries, at times in a peculiarly tripartite, eschatological and symbolic one, as found exemplified in the case of Joachim of Fiore [21]. Whereas a phase of dreadful ontological stillness is inevitable, the more so as continuously confirmed by the physical laws accounting for the limited status of the present human, so is the advent devastatingly affirmative hence positive of the Overman, as the very herald of an unimaginably superior era, far beyond, in sheer overhuman terms, the one solemnly predicted by Virgil in his own *Bucolics* [22]. Owing to an antithetical state of affairs, a state of stillness is, therefore, in condition to favor, or rather to grant altogether the advent of an empowered one. For, again, the more this stillness in the former accumulates, the more devastatingly powerful is the return unto the very core most energetic on part of the latter, in terms historical, thus microcosmic or otherwise man-related, yet still centered on the frame of the Overman. This still wears a primordial aspect of historical verity, alongside its own peculiarly mythical one [23], in proving thus foreign to whatsoever stillness and still a necessary centrality or core point of reference (without whom the mere periphery would prove prevailing, with disastrous consequences) or otherwise dreadful Chaos, as opposed to the Logos. The symmetrical, hence dialectical force in history, as directed towards its own natural aim and destination precisely, is one, therefore, with the realization, or rather dazzling recreation on the planet earth,

that is, into still a dreadful obscure status of intrinsic limitations and impotence, the elected counterpart status of power of the Overman in the person of the letter himself as embodying the leading trait, as the Force of Becoming within the Triad of Power whose final relevant energy condensates into a majestic cosmic finale as new rebirth, as it shall be set forth. Whereas proven individual superiority can solely be associated, in terms of superior, hence true essence, with the opposed Overman alone, this recreation touches instead endeavors referring, in terms of responsibility and indeed overhuman manifestation, to an entire superior community, or nation, or empire etc., whatsoever might prove from time to time the grandest case. To set forth further, aristotelically, therefore thomistically, a potential thing ($\delta\acute{\upsilon}\nu\alpha\mu\iota\varsigma$, potentia), in its potential amount of energy considered, may prove much more powerful than a merely present thing ($\acute{\epsilon}\nu\acute{\epsilon}\rho\gamma\epsilon\iota\alpha$, actus). This would further occur by means of a permeation, as itself a prerequisite of motion, of opposites, the Overman and man, this latter still in his daily recurring miseries and banalities, whose nature his own faulty physical appearance with distinctness embodies [24]. Now the Overman, since still not here in terms of his own cosmic era [25], may prove just thus, as a selective destination properly, more especially *through a continual empirical wanting in man*. For opposites are essential for their own existence by their maintaining a decisive role in relation to the entire process, whether historical or cosmic in kind, the latter proving at length ontologically superior to the former, as it shall be seen. Becoming hence history cannot, therefore, as a matter of course arrest itself until the actual time of the Overman shall make, again, its own, in terms most dazzling regarded or else photonic [26], crucial apparition as thus further antithetically favored by a status of obscure decadence within an already impotent one, in terms now set forth of historical principle. To add more, within the present status of the universe, which is of dreadful ontic impotence as visibly and physically exemplified in man, wherein, not by chance, a mere microorganism can prove fatal, the dominance (momentary) of one form leads, antithetically, to the increase in power into another, this latter as thus proving the sole conquering, hence superior and ontologically true. This boost is, in terms of becoming by definition itself continually increasing, always addressed to an achieved degree, which, at a human level, cannot but refer to the opposite counterpart of power embodied by the Specular Overman, whose dazzling ultimate person *embodies again the aim, the accomplishment, the completion, the perfection (specular in kind), the totality, and the fullness*. Touching proven individual value, the scheme (highly selective) is thus as follows:

Identity as Self-Overcome \rightarrow True Identity (as Selective) \rightarrow Overman as Over-Identity [27]

For

The Force of Becoming favors, antithetically, in terms of Potentiality, or of *latent Energy within the Potential*, to the Overhuman Act as incarnating the

True Selective Identity, at once into the Future and the Past [28]

As regards this potentiality-actuality relationship now considered (Potentia-Actus), indeed simple and primordial, more than ever valid as rooted in whatsoever change as a chief trait in material Ens, which relationship may well be extended into the one defining thus matter (Materia) and form (Forma) and in turn, even more radically, or the one in other respects touching essence (Essentia) and existence (Existentia), all thus in the relevant metaphysical terms of *continual alteration over time*, the process is looked upon in view of a distance basically infinite and inevitably cosmological in kind (ad Universum), as dwelling between the Overman as the very necessary embodiment of sheer Perfection, hence of the very category *Power* itself as wearing an aspect of unrivalled ontological primacy [29] and man as, conversely, the visible manifestation of defect, want, misery and in the end powerlessness, to which the doom of ontic dissolution lies not unproportionally, much less inappropriately referred.

Symmetrical Strength and Specular Intensity

By thus further touching *the conception of finality*, it may well be observed that it proves to be *either that in view of which an action takes place, or as the accomplishment of that to which the action comes otherwise directed*, in a manner thus firmly considering adversity, of whatsoever kind, as dramatically, that is, irreversibly in relation to action of the *Intangible Time* [30], dwelling intrinsic to the otherwise *Fiery Ens* (entity), hence to the Real as a whole, as thus rendered further miserable, when referred to its present status of ontological-physical, non-photonic in kind limitation [31]. In both cases thus, concrete direct action and relevant sheer conviction are implied in reference to a well-defined aim, which latter in turn entailing an objective, a direction, a guidance, a tendency, an execution, a realization, as thus related to the agency found in the one of will itself. It is not much to further say that without vigour, personal and inner, and of course superior in kind as related to an individual of proven value, there can be no effective or energetically confirmed upon a practical level, actual will nor volition, whereas without these latter *there can still be energy, as consciously directed to an aim*. Hence *Energy as Will* (and not the converse, inasmuch as solely a moral criterion) stands as independent and ontologically prevailing for, by reference to the omnipresence (still selective) of the Overman, *Energy and Will* are both fully realized into the dazzling frame of the latter, a frame that knows, *and must know not, antithetically*, no limitation whatsoever in the terms of sheer ontological-physical potency, which potency is to transcend accordingly even dissolution or death as representing the ultimate ontological defeat the *Physical Ens* (thus entailing the human in its present state of impotence). The Force of History focalizes therefore, consciously even though hiddenly (for the person of the Overman cannot be of course tangibly seen, *if not in the ultimate terms of the Core of Becoming as one with it*, as it shall be illustrated) on a well-

defined antithetical aim. This aim proves, on the one hand, collective and always sacrificial (since always involving gore, sometimes shed by millions of individuals, as in global wars) whenever thus referred to the mass, and on the other an invisible incarnation, *sheer individual* as the natural ultimate outcome of change, inevitably cosmic in character as transcending historical events on this planet. Hence, the hidden yet dazzling presence of a selective destination is *always antithetically yonder*, on account of the force of perpetual Becoming (as still being considered in reference to its own essence, which must be foreign to whatsoever beginning or end), a destination driven by, and at length fully one with a most potent, as it were, directing turbine, with its spiral-like impetus increasing an inner amount of ontological-physical potency to an ultimate ∞ [32]. For this very impetus (the grandest, alongside Being as Power, to be found dwelling into the dazzling frame of the Overman in the terms of Triad of Power he himself, with his own action thus, presides over) is aimed to *it's a necessary self-referential state of perfection*, inevitably found *most simple* in reference to a core-metaphysical reasoning, both hence Greek and Patristic [33]. This leads to the awaiting *absolute unity, oneness and union, hence in the end to the very origin itself*, upon a *relevant state of fiery infinity closing majestically on itself*, by aid of a relevant spiral-like cosmic phenomenology (to which spiral-like phenomenology, the form peculiar to galaxies may well be associated [34], by now assuming possibly *the one in an all-powerful Dragon* [35]), and in further reference to an all-gathering ultimate Momentum. As for the former suggestion, the following brief literary one, in an archaic Scottish tone:

Saw Ah! Saw Ah noo! lookin' yondir!
 Before my ain verra eyes,
 The Verra Nucleus wi'in Total Gravity dwellin'!
 The Verra Core, Ah say noo to ye,
 Frae Fathomless the Wniverse!
 Intae the Becoming Unforgivin', IT!
 An' waes IT, waes IT!
 Let me, noo, distinctly remember, IT!
 In Spiral Shape of *Red Dragon*
 Hys Open Verra Jaws
 Core-Enraged.

In view of a symmetrical strength and specular intensity (most selectively so, else the *Ens foreign to Dignity* would also recur, which is an ontological blasphemy) to be found within the constant and relentless Becoming, a most variegated imperfection touching the present status of the human, and in its altogether faulty ontological-physical nature proves thus again antithetical to this tangible destination, whose aspect of opposite sheer ontological-physical Power the dazzling very Body of the Overman alone, as thus most unimaginably distant in both space and time, is in condition to altogether wore. The latter finds thus himself so habited in his own cloak of Dazzling Fire, most tangibly photonic in kind [36], and cut, moreover, in the flowing character

of Gory History itself, as to dwell a supreme Sovereign into his own Primal Regions of Light, with which he is perfectly one, through a geometric harmony equally fully realized as supreme, and as a goal beyond the unforgiving Change. As the present status of the human, including whatsoever decadence (as proving always momentary), is less than a *quark* within an unfathomable receptacle (whose core cannot but be most energetical, or rather, in a sheer Heraclitean manner still, *Fiery*, as it shall be seen), an immortal Heraclitean dialectical truth and validity lies thus into the relationship that sheer superiority, that is, the individual of proven value, maintains with the specular (again, most selectively so) Overman throughout time, hence *with collective history itself*, as himself, despite his utter limitations as ending in death, forming unquestionably a part in it. For, again, in terms of ultimate destination, beyond or behind the Overman as now one with the core of Becoming, one may find himself encountering nothing but the hideous Very Void: the non-Being itself, the feeble, passive and static yet still dreadful empty non-Ens, in terms Parmenidean, alongside its own intrinsic amount of horror (as *Horror Vacui*, precisely). Upon the Essence of Man being *over and over unto the Very Infinite* exceeded by the one (supreme, as now a destination) in the Overman (beyond whom there dwells but Nothingness in person), the more so when the latter *now* comes exemplified in the nobility of a progression proving ultimately historical gore, *now* transcends the present human's own most limited status as singularly considered (as not, therefore, able to bear alone the weight from an epochal gravity), and *now* refers to his own Very Frame as the necessary central outcome of Becoming (wherein Change still proceeds as further Increase in ontic Power [37]), this dialectical truth lies still bound to an ancestral message, which is the one in the Fiery Logos itself. This in accordance with the view that history, in a manner akin to individual existence, still yield to the Hobbesian law of causation in terms of chain of events forming an order [38], *or disorder rather*, from a non-deterministic or else chaotic perspective, as confirmed by the general character of the present human [39]. Into the chief and grandest moments of this dramatically enflamed, as well as unrelenting thread (in whose regard a *backwards direction* not even the mightiest deity, as proving by definition impotent towards the irreversible past, is able to assume), thus always involving strife or gore, the Overman grows a conqueror, *towards both the past and the present as a unchangeable certainty, and the future as an open possibly*, in his thus embodying to perfection the most dynamic character in the Triad of Power, a trait which is, conversely, altogether foreign to Chaos, hence, since the very dawn of Rational Thought, to overall Ontological Falsity. Again, the Overman alone is in condition to incarnate this, as thus self-rendered most remarkable by his own dazzlingly superior, unto the infinite so, ontological dignity as the Aim and the Mover (for, he is Pure Action and that in view of which this action takes place), throughout a process which himself thus embodies, and of which iconographical instances in great plenty may be given, at Hattusa, at Mycenae, at Persepolis, at Tadmor, or at

the Scandinavian Ørsta, all giving evidence of an over-human presence in a collective exertion, thus standing as both *hieratically and unconsciously* perceived [40]. This phenomenology lies akin to the one expressing the highest levels of frequency in the wavelength of the electromagnetic spectrum, as recognizable in events indicating, from time to time, an intenser amount of historical gravity (such as at Thermopylae, at Teutoburg, at Hastings etc.), with whom the single sheer overhuman presence identifies. It is, therefore, as it were, undulatory in kind (for into the grandest events alone a sheer beyond-human manifestation can effectively occur), witnessed moreover by a relevant catalyzing presence of intangible *Quanta of Power* [41]. As a natural tendency to stability and self-preservation prevails (else the human would vanish from the face of the globe), notwithstanding an innate impulse to self-destruction on account of continual antagonizing forces, the essence of history proves, hitherto, *the most ontologically feeble before its very Aim*, excepting the very impetus afforded by the Very Origin as Antiquity (in which the Bronze Age has thus a priority) as well by the ironclad, as it were, ontological severity in the subsequent Middle Ages, the whole process still not reaching his own supreme state, as driven by change as directed towards its own, which state is the form dominated by the frame of the Overman, as regularly recurring over a self-increasing in power spiral-like advancing, thus exceeding the one crystallized in the mere cyclical one [42], and therein unto infinity hurling its own directing blows, unto a point wherein this rotating spiral shall meet with its own point of absolute Radiant Energy, still under the garb of Core-Body, as it shall be seen. To this a symmetrical strength a specular intensity may be added, *still unconscious and sacrificially collective* in its own destination towards the latter, through an equilibrium surfacing from within the mass, and touching the action from single excellence alone. In drawing the argument to a close, the following scheme is propounded:

OVERMAN AS INCARNATED
CATALYZATION
(ONTOLOGICAL, PHYSICAL)
Hence

OVERMAN AS MOVER AND AIM
(SELECTIVELY INDIVIDUAL, OVER-
HISTORICAL, COSMIC)

Hence

OVERMAN as EEXATON IIYP

Glare-Overman, Will-to-the Overman, Ultimate Inward Fire

Most assuredly, a rain of arrows on a battlefield is a vivid affirmation of the power of a multitude, all at once still randomly manifested, owing to no precise individual target being addressed by the archers at the beginning of the clash *but the enemy mass*. In a similar

although diverging manner, the Heraclitean Fire, as foreign to whatsoever antonym or contradiction, encompasses this multitude, or else plurality, by nevertheless exceeding the latter insofar as a directing, devastating and *most rational* (else the self-inflicted doom shall be destruction) force holding its dominion over the chaos [43]. This ancestral turn of mind dwells since millennia at the very heart of the Logos, hence thus must be *in perpetuum* received. Yet by fathoming the question further, there is more to add, and to in the end surpass in terms of sheer personification. For this remains necessary in dealing with events proving human, as an exigency the very essence of overhuman alone can accordingly fulfill touching his own character of self-agency, in a word, again of Eskaton Pyr, of which history is left to the guidance, and in which everything is surpassed in reference to the notion of Triad of Power, wherein the Person of the Overman dwells a sovereign [44]. To further explain, now in terms of actual possibility or rather fact: over a time long since gone its way into an infinite region, within the starry walls encircling high, a fathomless Real, in more than a trillion of related possibilities or accidents, *one occurs, at length, as the presence of the Overman*. If we are further wont to regard the whole force of the universe, or of the universes as exceeded into the Very One (for, of course, the rival notion of “multiverse” remains altogether questionable, the cosmos, proving otherwise *the Universum, the Oneness*), that force is, equally, the fiery *Unicum Movens*. This being established, it may be worth observing that the nature of human history yields before the physical, as its at present so dramatically experienced (so much, in fact, as to allow the antithetical presence of a perfectly realized frame and status). Whereupon the conception of the cosmos as exceeding, hence comprising whatsoever historical instance, alongside sheer pragmatic ones as a matter of course follows, that is, respecting the Abstract as realized into the sheer Fact, with the result that whatsoever unmistakable conviction must again meet with Concrete Action, else no conviction properly so termed would be the case, much less truth. On looking closely, true ontological motion entails therefore again a destination and finality, still most dynamic one, hence, from a perspective Aristotelian to be now fathomed, a most self-referential *first mover* (else motion, as even *exceeded in the terms of quantity of motion*, thus embodying the Essence of Time itself, which Essence, as the nature of the Titan *Kronos*, never shows any mercy, would be devoid of its own very beacon, thus meaning). The question remains unaltered, since this state of affairs, on one hand proves individual by its embodying a specular identification and opposed counterpart, in both cases selective to the highest degree [45], on the other, it proves *collective* in this manner revealing its imperceptible historical presence now at issue: for the shades in the manifestation of this presence are not the shades of just any one entity, but rather of a multitude of entities, changing in their tones from historical event to historical event, always in magnitude crucial, thus reveling an unparalleled beyond-human insofar as epochal trait. As for this second instance, beside embodying the very mover within historical events (collectivity thus proving, from a non-anthropocentric

perspective, again merely peripheral), the Person of the Overman is the cause in cosmic becoming as referred to the ultimate phases of the latter, in possible view of the fact that rational deduction may still lead, very straightforwardly, to the unthinkable itself, still a rational one, that is, to the catalyzing, by necessity fiery core within deep the unexplored, either by the mind or through empirical investigation, recesses of the Physical Real. This is held to occur in relation to a most remote epoch of the latter, in whose abode everything, hence ultimately the *Ens itself*, grows a prey to an unparalleled unified force or the one we are accustomed in perceiving as *gravity*. Herein Eternal Mutation still dwells (for Becoming in any case, as to its own essence, meets with no limit) by holding its dominion over all, hence, again, over historical events as themselves deriving from the superior force in an unfathomable and immanent cosmic Physical. This radiant point of limitless Vigor proves to be again one with the frame of the Overman in his maintaining a privileged status in a surpassing Triad (the force of Being and Becoming dwelling alongside) which himself incarnates, in his dragging everything along (thus the *Ens in itself*) unto the very core of motion. Now this position lies still consistent with the Heraclitean Logos (Λόγος) thus fiery and unitary, hence most distant from dispersion and ontological feebleness in its still asserting the Cosmic Return as necessary self-referentiality of the *Ens* [46]. Now the difference in terms of increased ontological-physical Power is essential to the latter, else there can be, in itself, no recurrence altogether [47]. For the *Ens* proving supremely dynamic proves equally self-denotative to an ultimate degree. Now what can be possibly more dynamically conceived than the final, all-absorbing, all-judging nature of the cosmos in its own conclusive fiery stage, still further fortified as embodying the metaphysical Very Core in Becoming? Everything thus rushing towards its own self-referential Essence, a grand central mass, a prime mover (Greek *πρῶτον κινῶν ἀκίνητον*, Latin *Primum Movens*, in terms now Aristotelian) as embodying thus the primary cause, where and whereunto the relevant ultimate character of *Pure Action* still firmly dwells and is directed [48]. Now, as aforementioned, the character of the universe naturally implies that of *Being*, hence the conception of the latter in terms of Power. A relevant strong definition has been correspondingly employed, in relation thus to the *Ipsium Esse Subsistens* as opposed to the *Comune Esse* (as otherwise found in Duns Scotus, Wolff and Suarez), furthermore, with no possible connection whatsoever with a *Negatio Negationis* as found peculiar to Meister Eckhart [49]. This latter aspect has been again defined in the supremely dynamic notion of Triad of Power, wherein the person of the Overman prevails, and wherein it is held that the whole contracting force of the *cosmos-in-becoming* reaches its supreme recapitulation in having thus an unparalleled bearing on it (for nothing else is to be found beyond, if not in the terms of the Very Void, or the appalling presence, or rather non-presence of the *Non-Ens*), both unto the Future and the Past, as it shall be fathomed. The whole standpoint proves evidently referable to the category *Big Crunch*, under the garb generally received (by thus taking note,

in a Kantian perspective [50], of its theoretical, or subjective, limitations as still transcended into one single overhuman frame), hence to that of *singularity*, or a well-defined ultimate spatiotemporal *location* (still now a *frame* equally ultimate) in which physical laws, as mathematically described, yields to certain infinite quantities and values, in relation to a most conclusive universal scenario, still shaping the future (for beginning and end are, physically-metaphysically, one), which scenario evidently suits the case, in terms almost Wagnerian, of fiery final, as again confirmed in the solid Heraclitean prophetic view. A brief premise may ensue accordingly [51]. As is known, this theoretical enunciation, not even regarded, in certain ontological terms, as the most veritable one (hence the closest to that of ἐκπύρωσις), dwells upon the density of matter throughout the cosmos proving as high enough as to at length cause the gravitational attraction to overcome its own initial expanse, this latter originated from the Big Bang (which notion, one may well assume, proves *antithetical*, hence *inseparable* from that of Big Crunch as thus a counterpart). If one then assumes the possibility that the overall density of the universe is to exceed the critical at least one time, its present expansion shall continue in consequence for at least forty billion years. Meanwhile, the inner boost shall duplicate, with the result that the temperature of the so-called *Cosmic Background Radiation* shall reach a diminution of considerable level. Upon the primordial explosion being thus decreased in reference to its initial stage, all the galaxies shall eventually reach a point in which the expansion would arrest, in which the outward direction would prove so yielding to gravity as to grow the reverse, and in which the galaxies themselves, alongside all the other celestial bodies for the mind to conceive, would start to collide by reference to an increasing temporal progression. For an observer [52], the phenomenon would entail a shift towards the violet in the spectral lines, that is, a *doppler effect* or change of wavelength occasioned by the motion from a relevant source akin yet opposite to the one presently indicating the escape of the galaxies, and the relevant acceleration of the universe. For about sixty billions of years afterwards (notwithstanding such all-comprehensive a scenario may well be painted in non-quantitative terms exceeding thus a mere point of number) the world shall meet with nothing but an ultimate and rather mild cosmic contraction towards a well-defined point proving certainly *unrelative* (since thus highly decreed by the non-human, extra-human *altogether cosmic* volition in the Great Reversal itself), and driven still by a slight increase in the temperature from an underlying cosmic background radiation. This action on part of the universe, altogether non-human yet still beyond human as still focusing on the person the Overman as the mover, is again antithetical, in its being equally imbued with an akin impetus, to the one in the Big Bang, the latter as a by-gone Shadow, when, conversely, the Big Crunch proves a conquering Substance still into one conceptual focus, self-decreed, which focus the Pythagorean Phylolaus, in his own quest for a dimensional core and ultimate point of reference, would have no doubt termed central fire or *hearth* [53]. Henceforth the

universe shall find its own galaxies occupying a mere one hundredth of their initial volume, when these, previously overspread throughout abysmal distances, shall start to collapse into a scorching amalgam: the superclusters with the superclusters, followed by the clusters, alongside their own counterparts in size, then the individual galaxies, until they shall all be mere constituents into a primordial fluid, the temperature of the cosmic background radiation meanwhile (although no temporal synchronicity may be assigned) rising to no less than three hundred degrees K. Over the next seventy million years the universe shall further contract and become thus millions of times smaller, with an increase in the motion of the gas from each star, and with increasing collisions amid different cosmic entities, such as black holes and pulsars, white dwarfs and black dwarfs, and so forth. Upon the cosmic temperature further exceeding three thousand degrees, all the stars shall run towards each other with a speed by now relativistic, and yet still be barely visible, on account of their surface temperature proving higher than that in the cosmic background radiation, this allowing some dark celestial bodies to be momentarily restored to their own burning life. For eight or seven hundred thousand years afterwards, in a cosmic temperature of ten million degrees or thereabouts, and with an inferno of thermonuclear explosions in quick succession (the Physical *Ens*, therefore, still meeting with the notion of Becoming as an Increase in Power, now inwardly directed) all the stars shall dissolve their own vigor into a hideously chaotic

blaze wherein electrons and photons would prevail, and wherein even the black holes shall at length yield to the, proving by now more than ever supreme, Force of Gravity. Consequently, upon the cosmic temperature reaching one billion degrees, even the nuclei shall start disintegrating into protons and neutrons, after which phase radiation would still materialize into pairs of electrons and positrons, the neutrinos resume their combining with akin particles, and the weak interaction meet first with the electromagnetic one, then with the all-unifying, into a self-decreed centre, gravitational. The so-called cosmic scale factor reaching by now a drastic zero degree, and space-time thus *collapsing on itself*, an altogether plausible Very Rebirth, with different physical laws, shall be by all means the plausible result, which laws shall all be *positively boosted*, before the opposite superior era of the Overman, *in sheer selective waiting* [54], under the garb, still, of historical, hence dabbed with necessary gore, *Eskaton Pyr*. From within this ultimate cosmic zone and scenario, *as witnessed, in impotence, by the hands upon the dial of a universal Clock, to recall the genius of Isaac Newton* (for Becoming, as metaphysically superior to Time, leisurely goes on), the image of a *Beacon*, now elevated to a self-increasing in force Infinity still distinctly emerges. This is still the Frame of the Overman into the *Triad of Power* he alone dominates, and now considered after the following image:

Fig.1
Excalibur

All the rays the beholder may now perceive gather into one solar surface, inwardly, thus assuming the form of lightnings and flames polarized by an invisible centre. This centre lies comprised into a solar surface in evidence top left, whose fiery rain the Overman, through his own shield, still in historical gore, altogether gathers. That is, he himself proves imbued (for no one else could, not even the mightiest deity as still impotent towards the by-gone) with an increasing impetus he himself dominates into the Triad of Power, by again thus proving one with sheer Becoming as bringing further ontological-physical power to the indestructible *Ens* [55]). This solar surface, or rather rotating disc (whose amount of Energy grows thus to infinity, by returning-to-itself over and over most identical)

is meant to embody the ἐκτύρωσις itself, as increased in a spiral-like force reaching (and possibly exceeding) the infinite ∞ . The legendary Arthurian sword can be perceived as merging into this primal inferno (positively regarded as one with the action in both the Big Crunch and Big Bang, both directed towards a single focus) at the bottom of a tower, melting itself into a fiery siege (for the struggle lies perennial). Now this Rain of Fire (that is, Becoming as Increase in Power) *so imbues the figure as to be in the on end one with his own person*. Hence a second figure is propounded, as semiotically bound to the first:

Fig. 2
Will-to-the Overman
or
Thunder-Force Increasing to ∞

This figure refers to the crucial conception of *will* in the first place, as directed towards both the Future and, by *antithetical necessity*, the Past [56]. That is, by still bearing in mind the Heraclitean dictum τὰ δὲ πάντα οἰακίξει κεραυνός [57], which dictum shall survive as long as human memory does, and by considering action

and its own effect *as directed towards the infinite since foreign to any beginning thus end* [58], in the face of whose ontological strength everything, *hence the Ens itself*, is destined to yield, this figure may still be perceived in the terms of Rational, All-Steering Force, giving hence the Primal Fire an ascendancy over all, into

the frame of the Overman as Incarnation (still necessary, in beyond-human terms) of Becoming (as the purest γίνεσθαι, whose very essence lies thus foreign to whatsoever *arrest*). Touching what has been propounded hitherto, this Becoming, by increasing his own vigor to ∞ , and by thus exceeding, materially, whatsoever entity for the mind to imagine, proves one with a *Locus Omnium*, or *Locus Locorum* [59], still into this very Body as precisely σῶμα, and as the very principle of universal motion (as Aristotle, or Averroes, or Avicenna, this latter in a more markedly neo-platonic tone, perceived in the terms of *Primum Movens*). An intrinsic luminosity dwells as reinforced by the flashing from the four lightings (which may be associated to the significance, equally quadripartite and now merely symbolic, in the four Hippocratic humors, in the four seasons, in the four stages of the life of man, and so on), which lightings catalyze upon the all-gathering, in terms of ultimate gravity, bosom of the ultimate central frame now at issue. One of these can be seen originating from the star visible top left, which star is meant to answer all the purposes, under the garb of Being as Power, of third perennially invigorating element to be found into the Triad of Power the Overman incarnates as Purest Action. For, beyond doubt, this latter signifies a communion of tensions, and the converse. It is therefore the law, the *measure* (τά πάντα, κόσμος-λόγος, μέτρον [60]), the eternal exchange, the all-judging Fire, whose intrinsically dynamic character and impetus, as well as *tangible mass* cannot originate from a ghostly Nothingness, nor to Nothingness return (since this latter, by definition, cannot embody any First Imposing Act). This process, on one hand defines a centre of propagation, cosmic or universal in kind, one thus of sheer gravity, in Ptolemaic or Copernican terms as altogether forgotten in the modern world, on the other a dramatic revolution, by increasing tenfold, then hundredfold and so on, until reaching its own infinite speed as metaphysical πρόοδος, or intrinsic unrestrainable progression. This so primordial an impetus, as further involving gore, from within the memory of history, when still in the terms of Eskaton Pyr considered, closes on itself, thus entering into dazzling combination with the outer rim in the figure, granting thus the process a self-referentiality opposite to whatsoever dispersion into nothingness as otherwise found in the linear view of time and the related open universe scenario. Herein the four (still Heraclitean in kind) thunderbolts meet in a common embrace, the infinite (∞) as consistent with a simultaneous increasing-in power direction *into both the Future and the Past*. An infinite growing ontological-physical force proves thus to be the case, which force, since still involving a *direction in life*, cannot but meet with the very meaning of *will* or *volition*. This is stressed in the same spiral-like charter of the figure, which is meant to signify the Will-to-the Overman, as thus focusing on his own tangible Body still, the sole thus to grant equally tangible *retroactive results*. Hence the following points, *to be all regarded in the most selective manner* [61], and in relation to infinite physical values, so overabundant hence as to meet with their own affirmative reversal into Will itself as both Very

Frame of the Overman and necessary central Outcome of Becoming:

Willing signifies willing the Overman as a Tangible Destination or *Corporeitas* both into the future and the past through a directing rational spiral-like continuum increasing its intrinsic force to ∞

And

The Body (*corporeitas*) is both *form* of corporeity (as specularity, since directed to the Overman as a Mirror-Image or *Eidolon*) and *matter* of corporeity (as filling the void from the past)

Hence

Willing signifies willing in terms of overhuman Body as *Corporeitas*

Hence

The Essence of Will is incarnated as *Corporeitas* (overhuman)

Hence

Willing is willing the Overman, both into the Future and the Past

Hence

Willing the past *as it was*, is willing the Overman as no longer a Blank

Or

The past is the Overman as thus willed backwards, and so is the future as empowered [62]

Or, in sheer dialectical terms,

Willing the past as Impotence is willing the future as Power in the Person of the Overman

And

The Overman willed, as a selective counterpart, embodies the future and the past as both empowered to ∞

Or

Willing backwards in the Person of the Overman, is willing the future as empowered to ∞ in the Person of the Overman

Or

Willing is also willing backwards, with both the future and the past empowered to ∞ in the Person of

the Overman

Or

Willing the past *as it was* in the person of the Overman is willing the future as empowered to ∞

And finally, by dwelling upon the prospect of superiority (ontological hence ultimate) as signifying the very measure of things, thus of the Ens itself:

Willing is willing the Overman as axiomatically one with the ontological superior, by thus exceeding the ontological inferior under whatsoever form manifested

And to conclude, by means of verses recalling a most potent primordial past, with the central ones now in Anglo-Saxon propounded:

THE OVERMAN! HE:
WILL, AS THE VERRA INNER ENERGY!
VIGOUR, AS THE VERRA INNER WILL!

FRAE THE PAST, FRAE THE FUTURE!
TANGIBLE, VISIBLE, INCARNATED,
NOBLE WYLD DRAGON,
SKYE-BEAST O' MINE,

GRYREBRÓGA OND FÆRGRYRE,
WUNDORA WYRM! ÚHT-SCEAPA HÉ!

FYRE-WOUNDED IN NAE GOWD-CAGE,
HE!

O'ER SKYE-SPIRIT O' MINE,
HE! HYNNE, UNCO SKYE-FLYIN'!
WI' HYS SKYE-GORE O'ER THE BARS
INVISIBLE
TRULY MINE AIN! [63]

In reference to the above suggestion, a next is visually propounded by focusing on the *element iron* as at once an element to be found within the universe and a peculiar, distinctive trait in the Middle Ages. The semi-otic connection with the previous figure (and the first) may be noticed in the ray and the shield:

Fig. 3
The Feudal Overman

This image still portrays the opposite Overman as wearing a 14th century armour, into which the very Last Cosmic Fire dwells, and wherein a found of thought may be gathered as to the relationship between *matter* and *form*, now conversely considered. That is, form itself, *as an outline of feature or contour* of person, still thus as $\sigma\omega\mu\alpha$ (body) foreign to whatsoever limit, and now imbued with primordial historical Steel, receives its own nature *from matter itself*, through an ultimate catalyzation, or condensation on part of the latter *as still the Big Crunch*. Although further foreign to any unity and alterity relationship in the terms of *progressio* and *regressio* [64], yet, still an analogy with the related conception of *coincidentia oppositorum* [65] may be underlined, as still the Big Crunch as one with its own counterpart, the Big Bang, whose supreme Flashing Fire, as a ray, reigns upon the gleaming (as still reflecting unto perfection Being as Power, inside the Triad of Power) most martial cuirass now in question, as well as on the dragon lying on the shield, therefrom emanating *in unison*, thus from the gravity, hence *not only metaphorical*, of the Middle Ages. Accompanied by a millenary, hence immortal criterion touching *the origin and the propagation as one into an ultimate reunion* [66], for the Overman still stands as

THE DESTROYER O' THE PAST,
 THE CREATOR O' THE FUTURE,
 O' LYFE FORE'ER CHANGIN'
 THE GREAT AFFIRMATOR,
 HYE SKYE-VEINS O' HYS
 O'ERHUMAN, MY AIN!
 THE IRONCLAD INCARNATOR
 AN' THE FEUDAL WITNESS!
 O' MY BURNAN MOUNTAYN-PATH
 DYIN':
 THUNDIR-FRAME O' MINE, HE!
 STRONGER! STRONGER!
 O'ER AN' O'ER,
 UNTO MY BY-GONE DAYS BLEEZAN,
 AN' THE ROARAN' FUTURE!
 AS MOLTEN SKYE-GOWD
 INCORRUPTIBLE
 NOO RETURNIN',
 WHAR IMMORTALITY ITSELF HYNNE,
 IN FORE'ER INCRESIN'
 HYE FYRE AN' BATTLE-GORE,
 O'ERSHADOWED IT WAES,
 INTAE DEEP THE WHYTE SPIRAL,
 SKYE-RECURRENCE INCANDESCENT, IT!
 ANE WI' THE LONE IRONCLAD IMAGE
 UNTO VERRA, VERRA PERFECTION!
 SKYE-SPECULAR O' MINE! [67]

This last figure still focuses on an ekpyrotic scenario, thus on the notion of singularity unto the utmost degree [68], in reference to nowadays categories and their own inevitable Kantian limit, alongside the Baconian conception, ultimately considered, of total dominion over the *Final Ens* [69], which dominion is now the one over Gravity the Overman alone incarnates *as the necessary outcome of Becoming and Very Centre of the (Cosmic) Real*. This centre is thus meant to embody a

unique all-encompassing ultimate force, at once physical and metaphysical (for the former trait proves consistent with the latter, as found confirmed within the birth of Western thought as $\phi\acute{\upsilon}\sigma\iota\varsigma$). And still under the most dynamic garb, historical thus inevitably dabbed in gore, of *Eskaton Pyr*, wherein Gravity is no longer an *obstacle* [70], very often a *fatal one*, a final narrative follows as the:

Glare Overman
 Or
 The Camlann Fyre

I found myself alone, standing on the high Red Rock. Therein the view of the universe was unto my blinded sight by now complete. For the heat was by now about me unconceivable, and the density of the Flame reached, in Lone Agony, its own Abode. For no dazzling event had been ever recorded as wearing a trait of so supreme a consistency. And heard I, loud yells of terror from the throats of countless of dying worlds, still convinced with the notion that the cosmos was open, and infinite within this spread. Yet the Seal was already decreed by the Central Glare. And I saw the whole atmosphere of the cosmos forerun, in robes of fiery Prophecy and *altogether willingly* (for this was indeed its own decision), by the Hammer of Thor, invisible, intangible, waiting for its own final devastating blow, floating into the astral void. Yet there were still words entitled to awareness, no mere lineage of spectators they, for an attempt was made on their part at grasping, by aid of their finest technology, the final substance of the universe, and at thus arresting its rush towards the Red Core. This was their final design and doom. For they all erected a massive barrier against the *Force of Gravity as a* seemingly impenetrable Stronghold, which was one for them all, and felt secure within *it*. Yet Will as Energy exceeded Faith, as the lone Invisible *Mjöltnir increasingly floated across the starless* space. It flashed its warlike ancestral hue at intervals, thus launching signals, but those they remained unseen. Meanwhile the contraction increased until one day (for there were still). This day was a day of great triumph in each of these worlds, a triumph they regarded as the final one in their battle against Gravity. Thus in one of their revels their general attention was arrested by an *ironclad figure*, previously unnoticed, who breached feverishly through the very gates in one of their defensive walls. He wore a decorated Saxon Iron Mask, martially engraved in Celtic spirals, and then advanced leisurely amid the astonished throng, unable to perceive any recognizable meaning in this. Hereupon they all endeavored to arrest his stroll in forcibly grabbing him, until they all discovered that his frame was untenanted by any substance but a Wild Mass of Contracting Fire. Thus the Glare Overman conquered. Thus I found this same Mask across my own path, and then wore it. It bore the inscription CAMLANN. And as my blood dripped onto the gleaming Rock cutting the ground with Fire from my own open scars, Will appeared as One with my own Image unto me forever advancing.

And as I beheld my by-gone memories within this Increasing Fire destroyed, this HE uttered, in a tone of voice absolutely *my own*:

THE WORN PAST DWELLS DEFEATED
IN THE FUTURE AS EMPOW'ERED!
INTAE THE STEEL-BLUIISH IMAGE AH HEARE
AM!
NOO AFORE THINE SKYE-BLINDED EYES
THRO' THE LONE HYE LOWE WOUNDED,
THAD ARE ALSO MINE! [71]

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